

Supplementary Information

ImputeCC enhances integrative Hi-C-based metagenomic binning
through constrained random-walk-based imputation

Yuxuan Du¹, Wenxuan Zuo¹ and Fengzhu Sun ^{*1}

¹Department of Quantitative and Computational Biology, University of Southern California, USA

Table of contents

Supplementary Notes	2
Supplementary Tables	5
Supplementary Figures	8
Supplementary References	10

*Corresponding author: fsun@usc.com

Supplementary Notes

Supplementary Note 1: Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) clustering evaluation metric

The rand index (RI) is defined as the percentage of correct decisions made by the clustering algorithm, i.e.,

$$\text{RI} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where TP is the number of true positives, TN is the number of true negatives, FP is the number of false positives, and FN is the number of false negatives.

Then, the Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) can be defined as

$$\text{ARI} = \frac{\text{RI} - \mathbb{E}(\text{RI})}{\max(\text{RI}) - \mathbb{E}(\text{RI})}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where $\mathbb{E}(\text{RI})$ denotes the Expected Rand Index.

Supplementary Note 2: ImputeCC’s genus-level analysis unveiled key genera and potential species expansion in the sheep gut microbiota

ImputeCC’s genus-level analysis, leveraging its retrieval of 408 high-quality MAGs, has unveiled significant insights into microbial composition of the sheep gut microbiota. Within this complex ecosystem, *Bacteroides* emerges as one of the dominant bacterial genera, well-recognized for its potential influence on the intestinal immune system [15, 16]. ImputeCC’s distinctive capabilities stood out as it successfully recovered two critical species from the *Bacteroides* genus, specifically *Bacteroides uniformis* and *Bacteroides vulgatus*, within the sheep gut environment. *B. uniformis* has garnered attention for its reported role in ameliorating immunological dysfunctions and metabolic disorders, often associated with intestinal dysbiosis [17]. In contrast, *B. vulgatus* assumes vital roles in reducing the production of gut microbial lipopolysaccharides and inhibiting atherosclerosis [18]. Notably, among high-quality MAGs, while MetaCC managed to detect the presence of *B. vulgatus*, other binning tools failed to identify the genus *Bacteroides* from the sheep gut dataset. ImputeCC’s distinctive capability also emerged as it was the only method that could detect the *Tidjanibacter* genus, a relatively new and less-studied taxonomic group [19]. This discovery creates opportunities for more research on this genus, offering the potential for exploring its ecological roles within the sheep gut environment. Within the *Rikenellaceae* family, ImputeCC’s analysis illuminated the prevalence and diversity of the *Alistipes* genus, which was predominantly found in the gastrointestinal tracts of the healthy human microbiome [20, 21]. Specifically, ImputeCC retrieved 17 high-quality MAGs affiliated with *Alistipes*, compared to the 4, 3, and 9 high-quality MAGs recovered by MetaTOR, bin3C, and MetaCC, respectively. Among these 17 MAGs, *Alistipes senegalensis* emerged as a noteworthy species, recognized for its involvement in mannose fermentation [22], suggesting a role of the members from the *Alistipes* genus within the sheep gastrointestinal tract’s intricate ecosystem. Furthermore, ImputeCC’s analysis unveiled five high-quality MAGs within the *Alistipes* genus that could not be annotated at the species level by GTDB-TK, suggesting the potential expansion of species diversity within the *Alistipes* genus. Additional experiments are necessary to gather further data on the phenotypic and physical characteristics of these uncultured members before their definitive identification can be achieved. In conclusion, all these findings underscore the unique efficacy of ImputeCC in advancing our understanding of microbial ecosystems by characterizing the sheep gut microbiota’s taxonomic composition and functional potential.

Supplementary Note 3: Filtering the incomplete reference genomes at the species level from the mock microbial community

The reference genomes of all species in the mock microbial community [1] can be downloaded from https://forgemia.inra.fr/metagenopolis/benchmark_mock/-/blob/main/reference/MOCK_001.fasta.gz. Notably, among these 71 reference genomes, the species *Methanococcus maripaludis* includes two strains (S2 and C5), and the species *Shewanella baltica* also comprises two strains (OS185 and OS223). Given our focus on species-level analyses, we opted to randomly select the reference genomes of *Methanococcus maripaludis* S2 and *Shewanella baltica* OS185 to represent their respective species. Additionally, reference genomes of the species *Desulfovibrio piger*, *Methanomasiliicoccus luminyensis*, and *Methanobrevibacter oralis* DSM 7256 were excluded from consideration due to their incomplete status. Consequently, we acquired a set of 66 complete reference genomes at the species level for the following experiments.

Supplementary Note 4: A standard read cleaning procedure

The removal of adaptor sequences was executed using the bbdduk tool from the BBTools suite (v37.25) [2] with the following settings: ‘ktrim=r k=23 mink=11 hdist=1 minlen=50 tpe tbo’. Subsequently, reads underwent a quality-trimming process using bbdduk with the parameters ‘trimq=10 qtrim=r ftm=5 minlen=50’. Following this, the initial 10 nucleotides of each read were trimmed using bbdduk with the parameter ‘ftl=10’. Any duplicate reads that were identical in terms of PCR optical and tile-edge duplicates for Hi-C paired-end reads were eliminated using the ‘clumpify.sh’ script from the BBTools suite (v37.25) with default settings.

Supplementary Note 5: The assembly of shotgun reads

For shotgun reads from short-read metaHi-C datasets, we employed MEGAHIT (v1.2.9) [3] to assemble shotgun reads into contigs with the parameters ‘-k-min 21 -k-max 141 -k-step 12 -merge-level 20,0.95 -min-contig-len 1000’.

For shotgun reads from mock Nanopore and mock PacBio long read metaHi-C datasets, shotgun reads were assembled with metaFlye (v2.9-b1768) [4] using the ‘-meta -nano-raw’ for Nanopore and ‘-meta -pacbio-hifi’ for PacBio reads. The contigs obtained from the two real long-read metaHi-C datasets (cow rumen and sheep gut) were directly provided by the original authors and downloaded for analysis. For the cow rumen dataset, Bickhart et al. [5] initially assembled PacBio raw reads using Canu (v1.6+101 changes, r8513) [6] and further refined the assembly with two rounds of Illumina data polishing using Pilon [7]. The finalized assembly is accessible at https://figshare.com/articles/usda_pacbio_second_pilon_indelonly_fa_gz/8323154. In the case of the sheep gut dataset [8], an updated assembly of PacBio HiFi long reads was provided by the original authors, who used metaFlye (v2.9) with default parameters. This updated assembly is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5228989> under the file ‘flye.v29.sheep-gut.hifi.250g.fasta.gz’.

Supplementary Note 6: Identifying single-copy marker genes from assembled contigs

We detect single-copy marker genes within assembled contigs following the strategy in [9]. Specifically, FragGeneScan [10] was employed to predict genes from the contigs, and the predicted genes were scanned using HMMER3 (v3.3.2) [11] with parameter ‘-cut tc’ to identify 107 single-copy marker genes that are conserved in 95% of sequenced bacteria.

Supplementary Note 7: The modularity function of the Leiden algorithm used in ImputeCC

Let G denote the Hi-C contact graph, where vertices represent assembled contigs, and edge weights denote the normalized Hi-C contacts between these contigs. The modularity function based on the Reichardt and Bornholdt’s Potts model [12] used in ImputeCC is

$$\sum_{\{i,j|c_i=c_j\}} \left(h_{ij} - r \frac{d_i d_j}{2n} \right), \quad (\text{S3})$$

where c_i and c_j denote the community index of contig i and contig j , respectively; h_{ij} represents the edge weight (i.e., normalized Hi-C contacts) between contigs i and j ; d_i and d_j refer to the degree of contig i and contig j in the graph G , respectively; n is the total number of edges in the graph G ; r represents the resolution parameter.

Supplementary Note 8: Estimation of the precision and recall for contig bins based on lineage-specific genes

Similar to [13], we evaluate the precision and recall of a given bin based on lineage-specific genes. Specifically, the bin’s precision is defined as

$$\max\{0, 100 - \frac{\sum_{s \in M} \frac{\sum_{g \in s} C_g}{|s|}}{|M|}\}, \quad (\text{S4})$$

where M is the set of all collocated gene set constructed by [13]; s is a set of collocated genes from M ; C_g takes on the value of $N - 1$ when a gene g is identified N times ($N \geq 1$), and it equals 0 when the gene is missing.

The bins recall is calculated as

$$\frac{\sum_{s \in M} \frac{|s \cap G_M|}{|s|}}{|M|}, \quad (\text{S5})$$

where G_M is the set of genes identified in a bin.

Supplementary Note 9: Identifying the species identity of assembled contigs on the mock metaHi-C dataset

All assembled contigs from the mock Illumina, Nanopore, and PacBio datasets were aligned to 66 reference genomes (Supplementary Note 2) by BLAST [14] with parameters ‘-perc identity 95 -evalue 1e-30 -word size 50’. The true species identity of the assembled contigs could be determined if there existed any alignment of the contigs to the species’ reference genome.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. The number of mapped Hi-C read pairs for the mock metaHi-C datasets.

Dataset	The number of mapped Hi-C read pairs
Mock Illumina	8,549,960
Mock Nanopore	6,079,873
Mock PacBio	7,844,386

Supplementary Table 2. The accession numbers (European Nucleotide Archive) and sizes of three shotgun libraries, sequenced using the Illumina HiSeq 3000, ONT MinION R9, and PacBio Sequel II platforms, from the same mock microbial community.

Sequencing platform	Accession number	Size of shotgun libraries (Gbp)
Illumina HiSeq 3000	ERR9765746	6.1
ONT MinION R9	ERR9765780	3.1
PacBio Sequel II	ERR9765783	5.4

Supplementary Table 3: The sizes of shotgun and Hi-C libraries from raw metaHi-C datasets.

Dataset	Size of shotgun libraries (Gbp)	Size of Hi-C libraries (Gbp)
Human gut	37.9	25.9
Wastewater	81.3	28.8
Cow rumen	52	10.1
Sheep gut	255	32.3
Synthetic yeast	17.3	16.2

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Fig. 1 Benchmarking using the real human gut and wastewater short-read metaHi-C datasets. (a) The number of MAGs with varying completeness (comp) and contamination (cont) $\leq 5\%$. ImputeCC consistently outperforms other binning tools, producing a greater number of high-quality bins in both short-read metaHi-C datasets. (b) The number of MAGs with varying completeness and contamination $\leq 10\%$. ImputeCC returned more medium-quality bins when compared to alternative methods for both datasets. (c) Comparative analysis of the taxonomic diversity at the species level within medium-quality bins obtained by different binning tools. ImputeCC's binning approach stands out by capturing the broadest range of microbial species in medium-quality MAGs.

Supplementary Fig. 2 Comparative analysis of high-quality MAGs retrieved from the sheep gut long-read metaHi-C dataset. (a) Comparison of high-quality MAG recovery using ImputeCC and three other Hi-C-based binning tools (MetaTOR, bin3C, and MetaCC), as determined through Mash analysis. ImputeCC successfully retrieved the majority of high-quality MAGs obtained by the alternative Hi-C-based tools, while also surpassing them by reconstructing a significant number of additional high-quality MAGs. (b) Annotation analysis of the high-quality MAGs highlighting the enhanced diversity captured by ImputeCC at different taxonomic levels in comparison to its Hi-C-based counterparts, such as MetaTOR, bin3C, and MetaCC.

Supplementary References

- [1] Victoria Meslier, Benoit Quinquis, Kévin Da Silva, Florian Plaza Oñate, Nicolas Pons, Hugo Roume, Mircea Podar, and Mathieu Almeida. Benchmarking second and third-generation sequencing platforms for microbial metagenomics. *Sci Data*, 9(1):694, 2022.
- [2] Brian Bushnell. BBMap: a fast, accurate, splice-aware aligner. Technical report, Lawrence Berkeley National Lab.(LBNL), Berkeley, CA (United States), 2014.
- [3] Dinghua Li, Chi-Man Liu, Ruibang Luo, Kunihiro Sadakane, and Tak-Wah Lam. MEGAHIT: an ultra-fast single-node solution for large and complex metagenomics assembly via succinct de Bruijn graph. *Bioinformatics*, 31(10):1674–1676, 2015.
- [4] Mikhail Kolmogorov, Derek M Bickhart, Bahar Behsaz, Alexey Gurevich, Mikhail Rayko, Sung Bong Shin, Kristen Kuhn, Jeffrey Yuan, Evgeny Pevikov, Timothy PL Smith, et al. metaFlye: scalable long-read metagenome assembly using repeat graphs. *Nat Methods*, 17(11):1103–1110, 2020.
- [5] Derek M Bickhart, Mick Watson, Sergey Koren, Kevin Panke-Buisse, Laura M Cersosimo, Maximilian O Press, Curtis P Van Tassell, Jo Ann S Van Kessel, Bradd J Haley, Seon Woo Kim, et al. Assignment of virus and antimicrobial resistance genes to microbial hosts in a complex microbial community by combined long-read assembly and proximity ligation. *Genome Biol*, 20:153, 2019.
- [6] Sergey Koren, Brian P Walenz, Konstantin Berlin, Jason R Miller, Nicholas H Bergman, and Adam M Phillippy. Canu: scalable and accurate long-read assembly via adaptive k-mer weighting and repeat separation. *Genome Res*, 27(5):722–736, 2017.
- [7] Bruce J Walker, Thomas Abeel, Terrance Shea, Margaret Priest, Amr Abouelliel, Sharadha Sakthikumar, Christina A Cuomo, Qiandong Zeng, Jennifer Wortman, Sarah K Young, et al. Pilon: an integrated tool for comprehensive microbial variant detection and genome assembly improvement. *PLoS One*, 9(11):e112963, 2014.
- [8] Derek M Bickhart, Mikhail Kolmogorov, Elizabeth Tseng, Daniel M Portik, Anton Kobeynikov, Ivan Tolstoganov, Gherman Uritskiy, Ivan Liachko, Shawn T Sullivan, Sung Bong Shin, et al. Generating lineage-resolved, complete metagenome-assembled genomes from complex microbial communities. *Nat Biotechnol*, 40(5):711–719, 2022.
- [9] Yu-Wei Wu, Yung-Hsu Tang, Susannah G Tringe, Blake A Simmons, and Steven W Singer. MaxBin: an automated binning method to recover individual genomes from metagenomes using an expectation-maximization algorithm. *Microbiome*, 2(26), 2014.
- [10] Mina Rho, Haixu Tang, and Yuzhen Ye. FragGeneScan: predicting genes in short and error-prone reads. *Nucl Acids Res*, 38(20):e191–e191, 2010.
- [11] Robert D Finn, Jody Clements, and Sean R Eddy. HMMER web server: interactive sequence similarity searching. *Nucl Acids Res*, 39(suppl_2):W29–W37, 2011.
- [12] Jörg Reichardt and Stefan Bornholdt. Statistical mechanics of community detection. *Phys Rev E*, 74(1):016110, 2006.

- [13] Donovan H Parks, Michael Imelfort, Connor T Skennerton, Philip Hugenholtz, and Gene W Tyson. CheckM: assessing the quality of microbial genomes recovered from isolates, single cells, and metagenomes. *Genome Res*, 25(7):1043–1055, 2015.
- [14] Mark Johnson, Irena Zaretskaya, Yan Raytselis, Yuri Merezhuk, Scott McGinnis, and Thomas L Madden. NCBI BLAST: a better web interface. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 36(suppl_2):W5–W9, 2008.
- [15] Tanya Yatsunenko, Federico E Rey, Mark J Manary, Indi Trehan, Maria Gloria Dominguez-Bello, Monica Contreras, Magda Magris, Glida Hidalgo, Robert N Baldassano, Andrey P Anokhin, et al. Human gut microbiome viewed across age and geography. *Nature*, 486:222–227, 2012.
- [16] Bertrand Routy, Vancheswaran Gopalakrishnan, Romain Daillère, Laurence Zitvogel, Jennifer A Wargo, and Guido Kroemer. The gut microbiota influences anticancer immunosurveillance and general health. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol*, 15:382–396, 2018.
- [17] Paola Gauffin Cano, Arlette Santacruz, Ángela Moya, and Yolanda Sanz. *Bacteroides uniformis* CECT 7771 ameliorates metabolic and immunological dysfunction in mice with high-fat-diet induced obesity. *PLoS One*, 7:e41079, 2012.
- [18] Naofumi Yoshida, Takuo Emoto, Tomoya Yamashita, Hikaru Watanabe, Tomohiro Hayashi, Tokiko Tabata, Namiko Hoshi, Naoya Hatano, Genki Ozawa, Naoto Sasaki, et al. *Bacteroides vulgatus* and *Bacteroides dorei* reduce gut microbial lipopolysaccharide production and inhibit atherosclerosis. *Circulation*, 138(22):2486–2498, 2018.
- [19] Zhiyong Xie, Yixuan Bai, Guijie Chen, Ying Rui, Dan Chen, Yi Sun, Xiaoxiong Zeng, and Zhonghua Liu. Modulation of gut homeostasis by exopolysaccharides from *Aspergillus cristatus* (MK346334), a strain of fungus isolated from Fuzhuan brick tea, contributes to immunomodulatory activity in cyclophosphamide-treated mice. *Food Funct*, 11(12):10397–10412, 2020.
- [20] Andrei N Shkoporov, Andrei V Chaplin, Ekaterina V Khokhlova, Victoria A Shcherbakova, Oksana V Motuzova, Vladimir K Bozhenko, Lyudmila I Kafarskaia, and Boris A Efimov. *Alistipes inops* sp. nov. and *Coproacter secundus* sp. nov., isolated from human faeces. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol*, 65:4580–4588, 2015.
- [21] Bianca J Parker, Pamela A Wearsch, Alida CM Veloo, and Alex Rodriguez-Palacios. The genus *Alistipes*: gut bacteria with emerging implications to inflammation, cancer, and mental health. *Front Immunol*, 11:906, 2020.
- [22] Ajay Kumar Mishra, Gregory Gimenez, Jean-Christophe Lagier, Catherine Robert, Didier Raoult, and Pierre-Edouard Fournier. Genome sequence and description of *alisticus* *sene-galensis* sp. nov. *Stand Genomic Sci*, 6:304–314, 2012.